

**DIRECTIONS FOR ATTRACTING FOREIGN INVESTMENTS IN
THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract. The efficiency of any system or market structure cannot be judged by the equilibrium configuration of its associated output. Because change is constant, it is necessary to consider how different coordination processes, both competing and complementary activities, affect the effectiveness of adaptation. The article is devoted to revealing the problems of regional economic development and solving them in the context of increasing its investment attractiveness. The purpose of the article is to determine the reasons for the underdevelopment of the region's economy and to solve the problems that ensure the formation of an effective methodology for increasing the investment activity of the region.

Key words: efficiency, adjustment methods, optimal production, general state of confidence.

In the conditions of stable rapid development of the economy of Uzbekistan, the issue of implementing deep structural changes, technical re-equipment of the production process and attracting investments to increase the competitiveness of the national economy is becoming increasingly important. During the recent period of instability in the world market, the decrease in the flow of international investments has slowed down the process of implementation of investment projects. The development strategy of the new Uzbekistan requires an

effective investment policy to increase the country's international competitiveness. At the same time, first of all, the introduction of innovative technologies, modernization of production, and scientific research are being carried out. Ensuring the competitiveness of manufacturing industries, attracting investments in the technological reproduction of the main capital, and developing entrepreneurship.

Investments and investment problems are widely covered in the scientific works of D. Keynes, P. Masse, C. McConnell, S. Brew, E. Dolan and other scientists. According to P. Massa, "...investment is the process of exchanging satisfaction of today's needs for expected future benefits.

The proposal to develop a program for the introduction of digital technologies both in the production process itself and in the process of production organization and management is substantiated. It ensures the improvement of the efficiency of production organization and product sales, ensures the production of high-quality, high-tech goods that are internationally competitive, which is a factor of increasing added value and income from the sale of manufactured products.

Investing in the economy means focusing on attracting real investments according to the nature of investments, direct investments according to the participation in investments and the duration of long-term investments. Unsatisfactory condition of fixed and working capital is proven. Development of a mechanism for creating conditions for increasing the investment attractiveness of agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan .

These conditions include:

- 1) availability of a sufficient resource base to determine the urgency of the problem, create conditions for solving the problem;
- 2) to determine the set of acceptable conditions for solving the problem;
- 3) formulation of problem solving methodology;

4) selection of a list of economic and organizational tools that ensure the application of the methodology developed to solve the problem.

5) Creating conditions for problem solving.

6) Consideration of the problem of increasing the investment activity of the republic's agriculture.

To study the relevance of the problem of increasing the investment attractiveness of the republic's agriculture. Study of the resource base to create conditions for solving the problems of increasing the investment attractiveness of regional agriculture. Learn the terms of problem solving to optimize resource costs. Creating a list of economic and organizational tools that ensure the application of the methodology developed to solve the problem of increasing the investment attractiveness of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In order to increase the investment attractiveness of the region, it is necessary to study the factors influencing the possibilities of effective use for attracting investments and their rapid development.

These factors include:

- ❖ state of production funds of agricultural organizations;
- ❖ the state of labor resources, their opportunities to implement investment projects for the development of agriculture in the region;
- ❖ the state of land resources, the possibility of increasing the land areas used for the implementation of investment projects if necessary;
- ❖ economic policies implemented by regional authorities that determine political stability in the region and reduce risks for regional agricultural investors;
- ❖ political and economic guarantees of financial incentives for investors' investments in regional agriculture;
- ❖ the availability of reserves of production factors in the region, which creates an additional opportunity for the implementation of investment projects in the republic.

The presence of these factors and compliance with the conditions for their implementation guarantee the timely development of investment projects necessary for the development of innovative industry.

Each of the listed factors has its own characteristics of participation in the production activity of the republic's agriculture, which determines the nature of the funds allocated as investments.

Having made a decision on the conditions for investing in the agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, we analyze the most important of the above factors from the point of view of investment attractiveness and determine what the conditions for attracting investments can be for the development of these factors. In our opinion, these factors include the main production funds and labor resources employed in the agriculture of our republic.

Forms and types of investments in the economy are considered. It was also determined that it is necessary to determine the nature of investments for attracting investments to the region, especially for the development of agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In addition, it is necessary to pay attention to the nature of investments, participation in investments in direct investments and attraction of real investments in terms of long-term investments.

Analyzing the influence of factors on the increase of investment activity, it was determined that there are main factors that are of great importance in increasing investment activity in regional agriculture. Such factors include the main production funds and labor resources of the republic's agriculture.

The main production funds of agricultural organizations are old and outdated, which was the main reason for the economic underdevelopment of the agrarian sector. This was the main issue in shifting the main burden of agricultural production to households and small agricultural enterprises.

The renewal of agricultural machinery and, accordingly, the use of advanced technologies in the cultivation, processing and storage of agricultural

products are carried out mainly in large enterprises. This process almost does not happen in small agricultural enterprises and households.

According to the results of the study, at the current stage, the basic production funds of agricultural organizations are being gradually updated, which has led to technological backwardness of the sector. In particular, this led to low investment attractiveness of the agricultural sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

It should be noted that in the last decade, the republican authorities have implemented an effective economic policy that helps to increase the investment activity of agricultural organizations and rural residents in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and to increase the investment attractiveness of agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The thesis shows the need to determine the nature of investments in order to attract investments to regional agriculture. Investing in the agricultural sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan means focusing on attracting direct investments by the nature of investments, participation in investments and the duration of long-term investments.

An approach to the analysis of factors influencing the increase of investment attractiveness of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan is proposed. This allows the distribution of the main factors: production funds and labor resources of agriculture.

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